

EXPLORING THE ROLE OF LANGUAGE LEARNING IN GLOBALIZATION

*N. Xalimova*¹

Abstract:

21st century is the era of where technology and trade and others are being the reason for globalisation. In this article, a deep look at the importance of learning foreign languages on worldwide connections.

Key words: globalisation, learning, culture, connect, language.

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Advances on different areas of connecting various countries is being one of the crucial causes for globalization which has a huge impact on our everyday life. Betterment of being in touch with other nations, the urge of running cooperative businesses, and realizing the value of an exchange education are connecting continents together, breaking the distances between people. In this case, learning foreign languages is one of the outstanding benefits of those who are going to keep up with global connections. This article covers some of the reasons why foreign language learning plays a vital role in globalization.

Learning language is becoming a must-do activity for all people around the world. No matter how old you are, a new language offers you countless advantages in your life. As many language communities are still yet to be studied, it's difficult to say exactly how many people in the world speak two languages fluently. However, current estimates predict that around 43% of people are bilingual, with a further 17% being multilingual.[1] The research shows that in 2024 almost half of earth's population is fluent in two languages, and about a fifth of living humans can speak multiple languages up to 5. Is this figure not proof for language learning to become humans' basic need?

A new language is a new opportunity. Foreign languages enrich your life by offering you a deeper understanding of the culture, mentality and history of other countries.[2] Language learning is not only about learning the alphabet, rules, tenses and grammar, but it is also learning behavior of society and its culture. The more you dig into language, the more you become aware of other countries' cultures, customs and habits. Simple question may occur: "What understanding the new culture, mentality of other countries can do with globalization?"

If you, as a business owner, will be able to understand the culture of foreigners, you will probably come up with different ideas which will appeal to foreign citizens. Or you can have great years of experiences of studying abroad without culture shocks and confusions. Being able to communicate effectively across borders and cultures allows individuals to connect with people from diverse cultural backgrounds, exchange ideas, and build relationships based on mutual respect and understanding.

¹ Nilufar Xalimova, 1st grade student of faculty of Economics, Andijon Institute of Economics and Construction

Over 7000 languages are being used as means of connecting individuals in the world.[3] Globalisation awakening the need of having certain languages to keep together the world. This language is English with an unstoppably growing number of learners. The list shows 10 most spoken languages in the world.

N	Language	Number of speakers (million)
1.	English	1.452
2.	Mandarin (Chinese)	1.118
3.	Hindi	602
4.	Spanish	548
5.	French	280
6.	Modern Standard Arabic	274
7.	Bengali	272
8.	Russian	258
9.	Portuguese	257
10.	Urdu	231.3

Only one language, English, because of its grammatical simplicity compared to other languages, is connecting approximately 1.5 billion people. Apart from being easy to learn, the English language is becoming so popular due to the influence of the British Empire and also English is the language of finance, trade and technology. 1.5 billion people can speak, teach, and help each other with a clear understanding of each other's words. 1.5 billion people are able to use internet sources without struggle because two third of information on the internet is in English.

I want to demonstrate the importance of learning foreign language with an example of the English language. It does not mean that you should not learn any other language, but English. The more languages you learn, the more opportunities you get in the century of globalization. Although language learning has many pluses, in this article, only one aspect of it has been discussed. Language is a key point when it comes to having global connections.

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